

LITERATURE RESEARCH PROJECT

IMPERIAL COLLEGE LONDON

DEPARTMENT OF MECHANICAL ENGINEERING

A review of bio-inspired morphing blade technologies for turbine applications

Leonardo Da Vinci's sketch of a bat-like wing design, circa 1487 - 1490 [1].

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Abstract

This research paper describes how the aerodynamic efficiency of particular animal species, among which are insects, birds and bats, is strictly correlated to the capacity to morph. In this scenario, morphing consists of optimally varying the shape of wings to adjust them according to different flight conditions. This ability, translated into engineering terms, can result in structures that feature a greater aerodynamic efficiency, a reduced mass and a longer fatigue life when compared to stiff designs, that are incapable of adapting to diverse operating conditions. Such advantages have encouraged researchers in the aircraft and turbine energy production fields to attempt developing morphing aerofoils. The ideal properties a morphing structure should possess are identified: minimal mass, high stiffness to sustain loading and at the same time flexibility in the morphing direction. Summarising, a high level of anisotropy is needed. In this paper, a critical review of the most promising morphing concepts available in the literature tailored for the field of interests just mentioned is carried out, with particular focus on horizontal and vertical axis wind turbines, as well as tidal ones. Both for wind and tidal turbines, cambering is the most popular morphing technique, implemented actively in the case of the former and passively for the latter. It is also shown how morphing can outperform conventional control systems, such as discrete flaps and pitching, in terms of power generation and load alleviation. A discussion on the main issues that still characterise current morphing designs is presented, in which concerns regarding the heavy actuation systems, the material of skins and the speed of actuation are raised. To conclude, the necessary compliant technology that would enable current morphing concepts to be actually employed in large-scale applications are disclosed.

Key words: morphing, load alleviation, aerodynamic performance, smart materials, actuation

Statement of the objectives

The objective of this literature research is to provide an extensive answer to the following questions:

- Why should aerofoils in turbines and aircraft applications try to emulate the morphing nature nature of wings characterising many species of the animal kingdom?
 - What are the benefits of morphing?
- What compliant technologies are needed to achieve morphing?
 - What are the optimal skins for morphing applications?
 - What core structures ensure the fulfilment of the morphing requirements?
- What are the most promising morphing designs tailored for industrial applications and how do they compare to conventional control systems?
- What obstacles hinder the development and commercialisation of morphing concepts?

The referencing style agreed with the supervisor and employed throughout the paper is *Vancouver*.

2021-2022 ME3 LITERATURE RESEARCH PROJECT

Meeting Log

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TITLE:	A review of bio-inspired morphing blade technologies for turbine applications		

Meeting	Date	Student Signature	Supervisor Signature
Week 2	11/10/2021	Francesco Riviuccio	Sina Stapelfeldt
Week 5	5/11/2021	Francesco Riviuccio	Sina Stapelfeldt
Week 7	19/11/2021	Francesco Riviuccio	Sina Stapelfeldt
Week 9	3/11/2021	Francesco Riviuccio	Sina Stapelfeldt

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1 Introduction

Flying is something that men have always aspired to. Ever since ancient times, emulating birds' physiognomy and wing dynamics has been a dream and a thematic of great interest for scientists and engineers. Starting with the myth of Icarus, following with the ambitions of Leonardo Da Vinci and the Wright brothers, the desire of flying has accompanied the evolution of mankind [2]. However, despite the many technological advancements that have characterised the previous centuries, man-made designs still struggle to be as efficient as the models presented by the animal kingdom. The reason behind that is linked to the rigidity of engineering creations and their ineptitude to be adaptable to different operating conditions [3]. Indeed, animal propulsion results in improved aerodynamic performance and reduced stresses due to flexible anatomies, that attribute to many species the ability to **morph**. Morphing, from the Ancient Greek (*μορφή*), describes the capacity to undergo a steady and smooth process of transformation which, in this specific scenario, refers to the ability to constantly vary the shape of wings depending on the flight conditions.

A great number of studies are being conducted to understand how morphing could be implemented in engineering applications and what practical advantages it could bring. Indeed, a large variety of morphing concepts has been developed for aircrafts, whose wing configuration determines the overall aerodynamic performance [4, 5]. This research paper covers the most popular morphing techniques in the aerospace industry, with a focus on helicopters and aeroplanes.

The potential benefits of bio-inspired morphing designs have aroused interest among many researchers working in fields other than aerospace, especially wind energy production. Due to the ongoing shift from a fossil fuel based society to a green energy one, wind energy production has become progressively popular during the past decades [6]. In order to satisfy the increasing demand of energy and reduce costs, larger wind turbines that can harvest more power at higher altitudes are being built [7]. This results in greater efficiency and power output, as well as higher stresses induced in the larger rotors. It is believed that morphing blades can help alleviating the aerodynamic loads, thus extending the fatigue life of turbines, and also contribute to enhanced energy generation [8]. This paper aims to discuss the most promising morphing concepts present in the literature for both horizontal and vertical axis turbines, including tidal ones, to inspect their feasibility, potential use and benefits compared to conventional control systems (hinged flaps and pitching). The crucial features that a morphing aerofoil should have, comprising optimal skins, cores and in general materials, are outlined. To conclude, a critique of the referenced sources is presented to determine the difficulties and obstacles of developing a functioning morphing structure and to establish whether the doubts that manufacturers and customers still have are justified.

2 Background theory on morphing

2.1 Morphing in the animal kingdom

The capacity to seamlessly vary the wing profile to adapt to different environmental conditions is a prerogative of many species of the animal kingdom, among which are bats, insects and birds. These three particular species, which display the greatest wing variations, achieve morphing in diverse ways due to their different wings' anatomies. Before describing the crucial characteristics of insects, birds and bats, it is essential to define the concepts of *passive* and *active* morphing. The former refers to shape changes caused by structural loads: in other words, the wing is given the possibility to deform according to the aerodynamic forces. Other definitions of passive morphing include the capability to autonomously change shape, without the need of a supplementary energy input. On the other hand, active morphing indicates the presence of an actuation system that is responsible for profile variations.

Stengel [9] conducted a thorough study on these three species. He observed that insects are characterised by passive wings, consisting of thin membranes and veins. As a matter of fact, they do not have a compliant musculature that allows them to actively change their wings' profile. Birds, instead, are able to tailor their feathers, their main structural component responsible for lift, to obtain enhanced aerodynamic performance. In the case of bats, the scenario complicates further. Indeed, due to their wing structure comprising an elastic membrane and numerous hind limbs, bats can achieve morphing in approximately 20 independent degrees of freedoms, as Figure 1 entails. This allows them to have great control during free flight.

Despite the outlined divergences between insect, birds and bats, it was found that all three are capable of cambering, spanwise twisting and variable planforming. The first consists of changing the curvature of the wing, the second refers to the twisting of the wing and the last one is related to changes in span length obtained by partially folding the wings. These techniques enable the three species to improve their flight performance and at the same time suffer minimally from aerodynamic loads. In the case of insects, twisting of the wings represents the most efficient morphing method, resulting in a 53% increase in lift force when compared to a flat plate model [9]. Maeda et al. [10] found that spanwise variation is usually preferred by birds, as they are able to modify the overlap of their feathers to increase or decrease their wing area by 18%, in order to either maximise lift or minimise drag. Finally, Guan and Yu [11] showed that cambering is the most effective morphing technique for bats. By numerically reconstructing a bat wing and comparing the

Figure 1: Wing of a bat comprising the elastic membrane and the various hind limbs [9].

cambering to a normal flapping model, they observed that the former resulted in a lift coefficient that was three times higher than the one characterising the unchanging geometry.

It is therefore clear that bio-inspired designs could have considerable advantages in terms of performance and fatigue life. It is also obvious that emulating insects' anatomy, thus implementing a passive morphing mechanism, would be the simplest and most feasible solution, given the range of smart materials available nowadays: the adjective *smart* is associated to materials that are either self-actuating, self-sensing or self-adaptive [4]. On the other hand, engineers' aim should be to create active morphing wings/blades by imitating bats' physiognomy, without compromising structural complexity. This would confer the greatest benefits to designs in terms of load alleviation and efficiency.

2.2 Morphing in engineering terms

As outlined in the previous section, morphing represents a promising solution in regard to load alleviation and increased efficiency for both aircraft and turbine applications. Indeed, adjusting aerofoils' shapes following the models provided by bats, birds and insects, allows structures to take advantage of aerodynamic forces in any operating conditions, rather than contrasting them. This reduces the stresses induced in blades and wings considerably, enhancing the overall performance [12]. Furthermore, morphing can help reduce the complexity of current flight control systems, decrease the overall mass of aerofoils and at the same time improve their aerodynamic advantage [13].

Nevertheless, developing designs featuring morphing characteristics represents a laborious challenge for engineers. As a matter of fact, morphing structures employed in the fields of interest of this research paper must present the unique requirement of being stiff enough to sustain aerodynamic loads and at the same time be ductile to enable shape variations [14]. More precisely, morphing blades/wings should be stiff in the spanwise direction, to maintain structural integrity, and deformable in the chordwise one. This implicitly suggests that such structures must be characterised by a high level of anisotropy [15]. This is essential because, especially for active morphing concepts, the energy needed to morph should be minimised, in order to avoid complex actuation systems and an overall heavy structure. The contradicting requisites of morphing aerofoils, that need to be lightweight, compliant enough to execute profile variation and sufficiently rigid to bear forces [8], make the development of such designs a demanding task.

In engineering terms, morphing techniques vary. Indeed, some shape variations occur in the spanwise (usually referred to as the out-of-plane) direction while others influence the geometry of the aerofoil (in-plane). It is important to mention that the various morphing techniques illustrated in Figure 2, which concern an aeroplane's wing, are also valid for wind and tidal turbine blades. This literature

research mainly focuses on cambering, twisting and spanwise change concepts, since these are the techniques that are strictly bio-inspired, as argued previously. It is important to mention that the common concept of discrete ailerons is not considered to be a morphing technique, as it does not achieve seamless shapes without introducing discontinuities in the profile.

Figure 2: Different types of morphing techniques (adapted from Basaeri et al. [16]).

To recapitulate, morphing aerofoils should be stiff, ductile and lightweight at the same time, in order to be competitive with the corresponding traditional designs. To meet these conflicting requirements, direction dependant stiffness must be achieved in most of the components comprised by morphing structures. In the case of aerofoils, the skin and the core must be devised accurately to attain macroscopic anisotropy.

3 Characteristics of morphing aerofoils

3.1 Skins

Skins represent a crucial component of morphing aerofoils. They are usually overlooked by researchers, who pay more attention to the actuation systems and cores. This is the reason why the majority of the concepts developed never reach the field testing stage [2].

There are different definitions of morphing skins. As stated by Previtali et al. [17], skins may be classified depending on their materials and their structure. Indeed, skins may be single layered, consisting of a simple sheet made of elastomers or shape memory materials, or could comprise a multiple layered structure such as honeycomb cells or corrugated patterns. These last ones are less common, as they are considerably heavier and do not always result in a continuous surface, thus perturbing the flow and increasing drag. Before presenting some of the most promising concept in the literature, it is essential to remember that skins should exhibit the same characteristics mentioned in section 2.2: high out of plane stiffness, high in plane ductility and finally reduced mass [18, 19]. An additional feature that morphing skins must display is the surface smoothness: this ensures that no discontinuities are present, avoiding the separation of flow and improving the overall aerodynamic

efficiency, in contrast to conventional aerofoils control systems such as discrete flaps [20].

Ott et al. [21] have conducted an innovative analysis on morphing skins and have proposed novel and promising concepts. It was argued that, especially in the case of camber morphing designs, the implementation of *Zero Poisson's Ratio* configurations and materials is crucial, otherwise spanwise deformations caused by aerodynamic loads could influence the strain in the chordwise direction. The importance of creating skins with a high strain recovery rate, in order to ensure high actuation speeds, was also highlighted. Three skin concepts were proposed to cover a triangular substructure: a pre-tensioned silicon sheet, a stress-relaxed silicon sheet and overlapping plates. The first two were chosen due to elastomers' capacity to experience large deformations before yielding [8].

The pre-stressing was necessary to avoid buckling of the cover when subjected to compressive stresses. In regard to the overlapping plates, polymer PLA sheets with a 0.6 mm thickness were arranged as shown in Figure 3. After conducting finite elements analysis on all the three concepts and the testing them with a loading machine, the following observations concerning the out of plane deformations were made: the overlapping plates revealed to be the strongest out of the three concepts, displaying 38% lower out of plane deflection when compared to the pre-stressed

Figure 3: Skin configuration employing polymer PLA overlapping plates [21].

silicon sheet, which at the same time was clearly superior than the stress-relaxed one. Furthermore, the additional stiffness provided by the plates in the morphing direction turned out to be minimal, yet it was not properly quantified. Although the overlapping plates proposed in this study represent a reasonable solution, it must be stated that the aerodynamic effect of the introduced overlap was not examined. A further analysis should be conducted to assess whether the aerodynamic efficiency of this concept is also favourable.

Raither et al. [22] have interpreted the idea of morphing skins differently. As a matter of fact, instead of aiming at a structure with constant anisotropic properties, it was deemed preferable to target a design with variable stiffness depending on the operational state of the aerofoil. In other words, when the structure is required to sustain loading, the skin should be stiff (in any direction), in order to avoid the need of assistance from the actuator stiffness. On the other hand, during morphing, the skin should switch to a high ductility state, to reduce actuator work. Two designs were proposed, one with electro bonded laminates (EBL) and another featuring thermal polymers. The former's stiffness was varied by changing the electric fields between the capacitor plates, hence modifying the attractive forces between charges. The stiffness variation for thermal polymers, instead, was induced by exceeding the glass transition temperature. These designs were tested both numerically and experimentally with a stiffness ratio of 20 between the rigid and the flexible state. The aim of

these tests was to assess whether these concepts could result in reduced actuation requirements. It was found that both designs were capable of sustaining the aerodynamic loads when switched to the stiff states and that they did not affect the aerodynamic performance of the aerofoil negatively. However, it was observed that thermal polymers had an adverse effect on actuation requirement, while the implementation of EBL resulted in 97% energy savings as well as an estimated 60% reduction in mass, due to the need of a smaller actuation system. Moreover, as the stiffness of EBL was solely related to the voltage applied to them, their activation speed was considerably higher than the one of the thermal polymers. Finally, an additional analysis was conducted to prove that EBL are able to modify their stiffness by a factor of 70, when switching between the states of 0 V and 3500 V, to hold a camber angle of 2° . Although the study did not consider energy losses, it is reasonable to say that EBL are a suitable solution for morphing skins and that their efficacy can be further improved by employing a low leak dielectric that keeps charges active over a long period of time.

To conclude, it is worth emphasising that the skin concepts presented in later sections usually consist of simple elastomers (often silicon) sheets, as they are the cheapest and most straightforward solutions. In order to increase the base stiffness of these skins, which would otherwise be too weak, researchers normally decide to use pre-stressing techniques. Nevertheless, as Ott et al. [21] have pointed out, permanently stressed materials suffer considerably from creep, thus making them unsuitable for long term application. Due to this reason, a discussion is carried out on whether the promising skin concepts employing either overlapping plates or EBL are compatible with the morphing designs that are disclosed later on in this paper.

3.2 Cores

As with skins, the cores of morphing aerofoils must also be characterised by anisotropic properties. That is why honeycomb structures with hexagonal cells have been a popular choice among researchers in this field. Indeed, honeycomb configurations display an optimal ratio between stiffness and density. They are also well known for their high out-of-plane compression strength [23, 24]. Nevertheless, honeycomb cells display room for improvement that would make them suitable for morphing in aircraft and turbine applications.

The most common honeycomb cells are regular and auxetic, with respectively positive and negative cell angles. Their behaviour under loading is substantially different: for example, the former contract when subjected to tensile stresses while the latter expand. Nevertheless, the large Poisson's contraction/expansion they both experience are undesirable, as explained by Olympio and Gandhi [25]. In their study, they underlined how an aerofoil should neither expand or contract during operation. That is why, they tried to first constrain any deformation in the non-morphing direction. However, this resulted in an increase in stiffness in the morphing direction. Therefore, *Zero Poisson's Ratio*

designs were investigated, by trying to stack regular and auxetic cells in different orders. Hybrid and accordion honeycomb configurations were created. As it can be understood by inspecting Figure 4, the particular arrangement of the cells allowed the two configurations not to experience any contraction or expansion in the non-morphing direction when subjected to a deformation in the morphing one, respectively referred to as y and x in the image. By conducting a finite element analysis, it was found that, as well as solving the issue concerning Poisson's ratio, accordion honeycombs resulted in a higher out of plane stiffness than conventional ones if the cells were thick enough. This makes them a suitable candidate for internal cores of morphing aerofoils.

Figure 4: Hybrid (left) and accordion (right) cellular honeycombs [25].

Ai et al. [26] further developed accordion honeycomb cores by making their stiffness spatially variable, in order to reduce actuation energy requirements. The objective of their analysis was to propose a concept that would enable the control of morphing by tailoring the in-plane stiffness variation along the chordwise direction. Therefore, great attention was paid to identifying the in-plane strength alterations corresponding to certain target morphed shapes. The stiffness of the honeycomb was adjusted by modifying the unit cell thickness and was calculated analytically through Equation 1. The parameters appearing in the latter are displayed in Figure 5. It was observed that the analytical actuation requirements agreed with the FEA, yet presented some divergences when compared to the experimental outcomes. This discrepancy was probably caused by non-linear effects in the components surrounding the honeycomb core, such as the pre-tensioned skin and the carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) actuation rod. Nevertheless, the validity of this concept, which met the objective of controlling the morphed shapes of the aerofoil and lowering the energy input needed to achieve them, was confirmed.

$$\frac{E_x}{E_0} = \left(\frac{t}{l}\right)^3 \frac{\sin(\theta)}{\frac{D}{T} \cos^2(\theta)} \quad (1)$$

It is essential to remember that honeycomb cores of morphing aerofoils concepts that are tested are usually made of polyamide or any other polymer that can be easily 3D printed or laser sintered [26]. While such solutions are appropriate for wind tunnel testing with small-scale models, a thorough study should be conducted to assess whether such materials are suitable for honeycomb cores that actually reach the field testing stage and are therefore implemented in large blades and wings.

Figure 5: Parameters of a honeycomb cell [26].

Lastly, there are other core configurations that could be employed instead of honeycombs, including corrugated structures and ribs. Nevertheless, the former are more frequently found in particular sections of the aerofoil, for example in the trailing edge as shown by Yokozeki et al. [27], and only in singular cases, such as the one disclosed in section 4.2, they are employed as main cores. The reason behind that is linked to the difficulty in covering corrugated cores with seamless skins, which increases the possibility of deteriorating the aerodynamic performance of the aerofoil. Ribs constitute a simple solution, however they do not always attribute to the structures the ideal properties that morphing designs should have. Hence, it is clear that the advantageous properties of honeycomb configurations make them the most appropriate cores for morphing concepts.

4 Industrial applications of morphing blades

Since research on the potential benefits of morphing structures has its roots in the aircraft sector, numerous morphing concepts have been developed for both helicopters' blades and aeroplanes' wings. In the following sections, an overview of some promising designs is presented, as well a discussion on if and how they could be adapted to turbine blades.

4.1 Helicopter wings

The rotary motion of helicopters' blades is strongly influenced by parameters such as centrifugal forces, vibrations and changes in operating conditions. Indeed, helicopters move throughout different altitudes and the nature of the airflow around their blades can change abruptly. That is why morphing concepts for helicopters' blades usually target high activation speed and complete

autonomy.

By conducting a thorough research of the literature, it was noticed that most morphing concepts concerning helicopters' blades involve active twisting, that results in a continuous variation of the angle of attack along the spanwise direction and hence in a reduction of stresses experienced by the rotor. This is usually achieved either by either fixing the web of the blades' spar at the root and letting the flanges deform freely or by employing torque rods [2]. Nevertheless, twisting techniques that have been developed so far still struggle to compete with conventional flaps due to the added weight penalty that usually characterises them [8].

That is why, DiPalma and Gandhi [28] have tried to develop a concept targeting autonomous changes in the camber of helicopter's blades, in order to improve aerodynamic efficiency. More precisely, the aim of their study was to conceive a novel solution that allows blades to generate large lift forces in any environmental conditions. Indeed, in places where air is rarefied and hence has a lower density, lift generation is more challenging: this is especially true for military aircrafts that operate near desert areas. Their design employed Shape Memory Alloys (SMAs), positioned right after the blades' root. Large changes in temperature prompt SMAs to undergo a phase transition (in this case Martensite to Austenite), which is followed by a shape variation [5, 29]. This is displayed in Figure 6, in which the cold state corresponds to the Martensite, while the hot one to the Austenite.

Figure 6: Different states of the morphing section of the helicopter's wings [28].

Nonetheless, it can be predicted that this design is a promising solution to mitigate stresses. Indeed, the drag force on the blades is directly proportional to the air density. Therefore, forecasting the air density variation can ensure that the SMAs morph into the right shape to suffer the least from loads. This is something feasible also because more responsive SMAs could be employed to have a higher shape variation frequency. Finally, this design could be integrated with a system that inputs additional heat to control the profile of the SMAs actively. Of course, the energy requirements related to such addition should be determined.

The proposed concept clearly represents an opportunity for enhanced aerodynamic performance and lift generation of helicopters' blades and some of the design aspects, starting with SMAs, could

be adapted to turbine applications. However, both wind and tidal turbines operating conditions differ significantly from the ones of helicopters. Indeed, turbine blades are much larger and do not experience great temperature differences as they are located at a fixed altitude. On the other hand, they suffer more from separation of the flow and complicated interference phenomena that arise due to the vicinity of nearby turbines. This explains why most morphing concepts developed for helicopters are a great source of inspiration for researchers in the wind energy production field yet are not directly adjustable to fit turbine applications.

4.2 Aeroplane wings

Countless morphing designs have been developed for aeroplanes' wings. Among them, the concepts of spanwise deformation and twisting, which are feasible thanks to the level of existing technology, have been predominant. However, researchers have started considering other options due the disadvantages of these two methods. Indeed, spanwise morphing may allow an aircraft to be fuel efficient and highly manoeuvrable at the same time, yet it comes with significant weight penalties (owed to the sliding systems needed to either extend or to shorten wings) [2]. The same issue concerns twisting, as outlined in the section 4.1.

Takahashi et al. [30] suggested an innovative design targeting active camber variation. Their aerofoil featured a corrugated core, with corrugation applied in the spanwise direction. The core and the upper skin were glued together and were both made of carbon fibre reinforced polymer, a material that complements the anisotropic properties of the corrugated structure, whose thickness was varied throughout the chordwise direction. On the other hand, the lower skin was simply made out of a flexible silicon sheet. Actuation occurred through two wires, one attached at the bottom of the trailing edge and other fixed at the bottom of the leading one. As each wire was connected to a different servomotor (enclosed in an aluminium box), their tension could be tailored independently, thus permitting autonomous morphing of both the trailing and leading edge. This design is illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Cross section of the morphing aerofoil with a corrugated core [30].

Numerical simulations were conducted to prove the validity of such aerofoil. A 2D scenario with Re

$= 8 \cdot 10^5$, corresponding to a free stream velocity of approximately 20 m/s, were recreated through the MSC Marc software. It was discovered that a total actuation force of 500 N was needed to achieve a deformation angle of 20° at the back and 10° at the front, for a model that had a chord of 0.6 m and a span of 1.2 m. More importantly, it was found that the stresses experienced by the structure were lower than the permissible values imposed by the choice of materials. It was also ascertained that smooth deformations contributed to greater lift generation, in contrast to hinged ailerons. Finally, the aerofoil was manufactured and tested in a wind tunnel. The experimental results agreed with the numerical outcomes, nevertheless some divergences were noticed because the finite element model did not account for three dimensional effects of the flow. In addition to that, buckling of the lower skin was also observed. Therefore, it was understood that the lower skin should be pre-tensioned. To conclude, the feasibility of this design, especially in terms of load bearing capabilities under extreme conditions, was confirmed also experimentally. Nevertheless, the actuation time should be investigated and properly determined. Furthermore, a more detailed analysis should be conducted on weight penalties caused by the presence of servomotors. Finally, additional experiments should be carried out in order to properly compare the aerodynamic performance of the aerofoil to the one of models employing traditional control systems. Indeed, supplementary wind tunnel tests may highlight that achieving a smooth surface by gluing the upper skin on the corrugated core is not an effortless challenge.

Another promising morphing concept was proposed by Kuder et al. [31]. Their design was developed around bistable laminates. The latter have become increasingly popular among researchers in this field, as they are capable of retaining multiple stable states, while undergoing large deformations. In other words, multistable elements (instantaneously) morph into a different shape, defined as stable state, after a certain energy input is provided. The deformation induced by rapid switching between the different states is significant, making bistable plates suitable for morphing applications. Such elements are a result of residual stresses in the material, usually obtained by either pre-tensioning some specific fibre in the matrix or by thermal treating the laminate with sophisticated cooling techniques [13, 32]. The objective of the design was to exploit the high activation speed and the snap-through properties of these elements to tailor the stiffness of the aerofoil depending on the operating conditions. More precisely, the aerofoil was made flexible to enhance greater lift generation when cruising at low speeds. On the other hand, when aerodynamic forces started to be predominant, the structure switched to a stiff state. In each different shape, the bistable laminates presented different properties. To verify this, a numerical analysis with the ABAQUS software was conducted. It was ascertained that the $C_{L, \text{flexible}}/C_{L, \text{stiff}} = 4.4$ and that $u_{TE, \text{flexible}}/u_{TE, \text{stiff}} = 4.3$ (where u indicates the deflection). An additional comparison was carried out with a conventional pitching system immersed in a free stream travelling at a velocity of 20 m/s. It could be observed that the morphing aerofoil (in both the stiff and flexible state) enjoyed an advantage in aerodynamic efficiency, measured as C_L/C_D . Although this study did not determine the actuation requirements, as they depend on the way the bistability is introduced (thermally or mechanically) in the laminates,

it presents a solid foundation for other studies due to its innovative concepts.

In contrast to the morphing designs conceived for helicopters' blades, the ones presented in this section could be directly adapted to turbine applications, as turbine blades and aeroplane's wings share similar features. It is crucial to highlight that the revolutionary use of bistable elements for morphing has been recognised also in the wind energy production field. Due to this reason, many morphing designs for turbine blades comprise this novel technology and are developed around the same principles of the bistable aerofoil described just above.

5 Potential applications for energy production

Up to this point, some of the reference morphing concepts for aircrafts have been presented. It has also been shown that camber variations are the main target of research studies, as they can be achieved with the level of technology available today and can be beneficial in terms of both aerodynamic efficiency and load alleviation. That is why, cambering has been the most considered morphing technique also in the energy production field. However, other strategies may also result in considerable advantages, as the next sections show.

Before discussing the most promising morphing designs concerning turbine applications, it is worth explaining how the performance of morphing aerofoils is often compared to baseline models when tested at same conditions. Most authors employ two dimensionless parameters to carry out insightful comparisons: the power coefficient, C_p , and the normal force coefficient, C_n . These performance indices are calculated by making use of the *blade element theory*, a method that considers the forces experienced by a blade solely dependent on the lift (C_l) and drag (C_d) coefficients [33].

The power coefficient of a turbine is a measure of its efficiency. Indeed, it determines the amount of energy provided by the fluid stream that is converted into useful mechanical work.

$$C_p = \frac{\dot{W}_{\text{out}}}{\dot{W}_{\text{in}}} = \frac{\dot{W}_{\text{out}}}{\frac{1}{2}\rho Av^3} \quad (2)$$

where A is the blade swept area and ρ and v are the respectively the density and the velocity of the fluid. This parameter can be used to characterise the performance of both wind and tidal turbines. It is important to mention that the maximum power efficiency of a turbine, also known as the *Betz limit*, was determined to be $C_{p,\text{max}} = 0.59$ [34]. This value is purely theoretical, exactly like the Carnot efficiency for heat engines: turbines' power coefficients are usually much lower than 0.59.

In regard to the normal force coefficient, the latter expresses the stresses experienced by an aerofoil in dimensionless terms, by taking into account the components of the lift and drag forces that are

structurally adverse [35].

$$C_n = C_l \cdot \cos(\alpha) + C_d \cdot \sin(\alpha) \quad (3)$$

where α is the angle of attack of the aerofoil, as displayed in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Definition of an angle of attack of a standard cambered aerofoil.

5.1 Horizontal axis wind turbines

As mentioned in section 1, wind energy has started to have a dominant role among renewable energy resources. Nowadays, the most common structures capable of extracting power from wind are horizontal axis wind turbines (HATWs). The constant increase in size of these turbines has requested the aid of control systems, in order to lower the stresses in the rotors. Up to this date, the most common control systems for turbines generally consist of pitching and discrete flaps.

Figure 9: Cambering achieved through a hinged and a morphing flap (adapted from Daynes and Weaver [20]).

Haldar et al. [36] have shown how the former does not reduce the loads sufficiently, as simply rotating the blade cannot counteract the variation of stresses along the spanwise direction. Moreover, the effectiveness of pitching decreases with increasing blade length, as the rotor's inertia influences the actuation speed negatively. On the other hand, discrete flaps manage to alleviate loads yet they result in added structural complexity, high actuation requirements and significant weight penalties.

Additionally, hinged flaps introduce discontinuities in the blade's profile, as pictured in Figure 9, and therefore cause anticipated flow separation which generates an increase in pressure drag [37].

Ai et al. [38] have developed a camber morphing aerofoil that has become a reference design for other researchers. Their concept featured a Zero Poisson's Ratio accordion honeycomb core, as the one presented in section 3.2, with a CFRP upper skin and a pre-tensioned silicon bottom one. Actuation occurred through a CFRP rod attached to the trailing edge and placed at the bottom of the aerofoil, as shown in Figure 10. A servomotor was employed to either push or pull the rod, in order to induce a trailing edge deflection. The design was tested together with a conventional aerofoil of the same

dimensions on an outdoor rotating rig at a fixed angle of attack of 8° , in a similar environment to where MW-scale HAWTs operate. The results obtained were then verified through CFD studies and the following observations were made. The actuation force needed to produce a 5° camber angle was found to be 250 N. The deformation occurred in approximately 3.03 s. In addition to that, it was found that C_p of the morphing aerofoil was 2% - 8% greater depending on the operating conditions. Finally, it was also noticed that the stresses experienced by the morphing blade were 12% lower than the one affecting the standard model. The conclusions drawn by this analysis, confirmed by both experimental and numerical results, showed how the proposed design is suitable for HAWTs. Nevertheless, before installing the morphing aerofoil on a turbine, a more detailed investigation on the fatigue life of the different components should be conducted, paying particular attention to the silicon bottom skin. Indeed, the morphing blade was tested for a total of 10000 cycles, not 1-10 million as per industry requirements. In addition to that, the weight added by the presence of servomotors should be quantified and a better actuation system should be devised. As a matter of fact, a single motor/rod system would not be sufficient to induce morphing of a large wind turbine blade: multiple systems of this kind would be required, thus resulting in a non negligible weight increment. Hence, a lighter and equally efficient actuation mechanism should be employed.

Figure 10: Bottom view of the push/pull rod mechanism [28].

A study has been conducted by Daynes and Weaver [14] on an aerofoil with the same features and components as the one just presented. Their analysis focused on comparing the morphing blade to a model with discrete flaps. By employing the XFOIL software and testing the two designs at $Re = 7.21 \cdot 10^6$ and at a free stream pressure of 4.1 kPa, it was ascertained that the morphing flap could deflect 34.4% less than the hinged one and still result in the same lift. Prototypes were then constructed and it was determined that, for a constant angle of attack, the actuator work needed to achieve maximum deflection of the flap was 3.25 times lower for the morphing model. The same aerofoil model was also investigated by Daynes and Weaver [20]. They carried out a numerical analysis by reconstructing 90 m turbine blades with the previously presented morphing concept and with discrete ailerons. The models were tested at $Re = 6.44 \cdot 10^6$ and at a free stream pressure of 3.18 kPa. The results showed that the morphing flap could deform at a rate of $8^\circ/s$, deflect up to 30% less than the hinged one and still generate an equal lift. Moreover, 5.1 J/m were needed to actuate morphing in the set conditions, while 8.3 J/m were required in the case of the discrete flap. These additional analyses demonstrate the validity of this morphing concept.

Franco et al. [12] have also developed a valuable morphing concept for HAWTs. The proposed aerofoil featured a simplistic core, consisting solely of ribs. The outer skins alternated stiff and

flexible sections, mainly made of carbon fibre glass with varying thickness. A servomotor was responsible for producing overall camber deformation by extending or contracting some stiff arms attached to either the trailing or leading edge. The configuration is displayed in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Variable camber design employing servomotors and fibre glass skins [12].

By numerically comparing the morphing blade to a standard one at different wind velocities ranging from 5 m/s to 15 m/s, it could be noticed that the variable camber design allowed for an average load reduction of 30% and an average increase in power coefficient of 15%. It was also observed that the best improvements occurred at lower Reynolds numbers and that the morphing aerofoil considerably delayed stall effects up to a 15° angle of attack. Although the activation time was not examined in the study, these results were further validated by experiments on a small-scale model. The latter weighed approximately 7.52 Kg, with the actuation system consisting of 22% of that weight, indicating how servomotors are functional yet add significant mass.

Among the concepts that incorporate a morphing strategy different from cambering, it is worth mentioning the one suggested by Wang et al. [33]. The design features a linear twist distribution along the span of the blade, achieved by locally twisting the root and the tip of the latter. A comparison between a turbine with standard, fixed pitch and morphing blades was conducted with the aid of MATLAB. The annual energy production of all three models was computed. Simulations were carried out at a variety of wind speeds, ranging from 5 m/s to 15 m/s. It was found that the morphing blades resulted in a efficiency increase between 24.5% and 69.7% (depending on the operating conditions) when compared to the standard model. The variable twist turbine was also 3% - 5% more efficient than the one employing standard pitching mechanism. Nevertheless, the analysis focused solely on numerically estimated power production and did not comprise a detailed manufacturing plan and a material selection for the structure. On the other hand, Lachenal et al. [39] have developed and tested a functional morphing blade featuring twisting. Their novel concept included a skin, an actuation system and a pre-stressed structure. Actuation was achieved through the guide rods present in the skin, that made the aerofoil warp. More precisely, the upper and bottom surfaces of the aerofoil could slide relative to each other, thus generating twist along the length of the blade. Morphing occurred about a rigid cylindrical spar. The structure was pre-stressed, in order to release strain energy when twisting and hence reducing the actuation requirements. This configuration is shown in Figure 12. A prototype was tested numerically and experimentally and its

load alleviation potential was recognised. However, FEA and wind tunnel results agreed only for small twist angles, $-5^\circ \leq \phi \leq 5^\circ$, therefore further studies should run additional simulations on this model to ascertain its validity.

Figure 12: Internal structure of a morphing blade featuring twist [39].

Ali et al. [40] also proposed a morphing technique different from cambering. Indeed, the deformation induced in their design solely concerned a particular section of the trailing edge of an aerofoil. The structure of the aerofoil was made similar to a standard one, yet the trailing edge consisted of flexible material, as Figure 13 entails. Actuation occurred through 5 pneumatic actuation muscles (PAMs), which were pressurised to generate an input force. A total of 9000 N were needed to generate a deflection of 32 mm (equivalent to a 4° deformation). The aerofoil was designed to be placed near the tip of blades, as that is usually the area most affected by stall phenomena.

Figure 13: Deflection induced in a trailing edge segment [40].

A numerical comparison between a baseline turbine and one with morphing blades was conducted. It was deduced that the variable trailing edge design could improve the efficiency of the turbine up to 53.49%, especially at lower wind speeds. It must be stated that no details were provided regarding the actuation speed, yet it is reasonable to assume that the latter

is directly proportional to the rate at which the PAMs are pressurised. It is also crucial to point out that this design revealed to be suitable mainly for small-scale (domestic) HATWs, which are usually installed at lower altitudes and thus do not experience particularly large stresses. Indeed, it was also noticed that no load alleviation occurred, with stresses being more significant for the morphing design than the standard one at higher wind speeds (which rarely concern small-scale HATWs).

All the concepts discussed until now consist of active morphing, with energy input being required to produce a deformation. Nevertheless, Cavens et al. [7] have developed a design that features passive morphing elements that permit cambering. More precisely, their study focused on bistable elements, introduced in the trailing edge of an aerofoil substructure (as shown in Figure 14) to achieve smooth deformations. Unlike the concept presented in section 4.2, the stable states considered in this analysis were tailored to have a stiff configuration at low wind speeds and a flexible one at higher free stream velocities. The switching between states was solely controlled by the flap

hinge moment, thus avoiding the need of any actuation requirements. Indeed, at $v_\infty = 50$ m/s, instantaneous switch between stiff and stable states occurred. The performance of this concept was numerically computed by implementing it in an offshore wind turbine. It was established that change from the stiff to the stable state reduced the adverse component of the lift that appears in Equation 3 by 30%, thus alleviating the load on the blade noticeably. This result demonstrates the benefits that bistable elements can have in terms of load alleviation, considering that actuation is immediate and no energy input is required. Nevertheless, a more elaborate inspection is needed, to assess the difficulties related to the manufacturing of such bistable laminates and the tailoring of their stiffness so that snap through between states can occur at the desired condition. Finally, the complications that come with producing large enough bistable elements that can induce morphing of an entire rotor blade should be appraised.

Figure 14: Substructure of an aerofoil employing bistable elements in the trailing edge, with stiff state shown on the left and flexible displayed on the right [7].

To conclude, the most promising morphing concepts for HATWs have been outlined. It is clear that morphing can have significant benefits both in terms of load alleviation and increased efficiency and should therefore be considered as a valid option to replace conventional control systems. While active designs were found to be the most popular in the literature, passive ones employing advanced materials such as bistable elements have now started to arouse interest among researchers, due to their capacity to autonomously morph without the need of actuation energy.

5.2 Vertical axis wind turbines

In contrast to HATWs, which are mainly utilised for large-scale energy production, vertical axis wind turbines (VATWs) are usually installed next to urban areas. The reason behind that is linked to the reduced size of VATWs and their ability to promptly response to any changes in wind speed and direction. Despite the different characteristics of VATWs, the latter could also benefit from morphing, as the following studies and concepts show. Of course, as VATWs are less popular than HATWs, a reduced number of morphing designs tailored for this kind of turbines was retrieved in the literature. Nevertheless, some of the concepts presented in section 5.1 could still be adapted to VATWs.

Baghdadi et al. [41] have conducted an analysis on the benefits of active morphing for VATWs, especially in terms of efficiency enhancement. The objective of their study focused on optimising the moment generated at the rotor's root by varying the shape of the blades at each azimuthal location. Nevertheless, as this is not practically feasible in manufacturing terms, the authors decided to inspect the effect of morphing on blades that could optimise their profile after every 60° swept, as illustrated in Figure 15. 2-D and 3-D numerical simulations were conducted on this model, as well as on a baseline one, and comparisons regarding the estimated power output were made. It was concluded that the increase in efficiency associated with the VATW implementing morphing aerofoils was deeply influenced by the tip speed ratio (TSR), defined as the ratio between the tangential velocity of a turbine's blade and the actual wind speed velocity. The best improvements were observed at lower TSR, with C_p increasing up to 53.6%. Despite this result, it must be remembered that the authors limited themselves to making a theoretical analysis, without presenting a manufactured prototype. Moreover, no effect on load alleviation was mentioned.

Figure 15: Morphing of a VATW aerofoil every 60° swept [41].

Woods et al. [42] have developed and tested a design employing an active morphing mechanism for VATWs. Their aerofoil was characterised by a bio-inspired core, with ribs attached to a central spine resembling the anatomy of a fish, a pre-tensioned elastomeric matrix composite skin and an antagonistic tendon drive, attached to the trailing edge. Actuation occurred through a non-backdrivable pulley, as shown in Figure 16. A prototype of this configuration was built and tested in a wind tunnel together with a conventional hinged flap, at a $Re = 390000$ and a varying angle of attack $-15^\circ \leq \alpha \leq 15^\circ$.

Figure 16: Morphing aerofoil configuration with internal ribs and a pulley actuation system [42].

It was found that the morphing design had an average lift to drag ratio which turned out to be 25%

higher than the one of the discrete aileron, due to the great reduction in drag related to a seamless varying camber. It was also verified that 95% of the maximum aerodynamic efficiency was retained by the shape changing aerofoil over an angle of attack range equivalent to 9.05° . On the other hand, the flapping model could retain the same portion of its maximum efficiency over an angle of attack range 3 times smaller. Although the actuation speed and requirements were not investigated and a further inspection on those aspects is needed, this morphing concept represents a promising solution in terms of load reduction for VATWs. Nevertheless, it must be stated that, as with the designs employing servomotors, the weight penalty associated with pulleys should be assessed.

Butbul et al. [43] have moved away from the concept of active morphing and have instead proposed a novel design with passive blades. Their objective was to find a system for VATWs to replace pitching, after noticing that the latter still struggles to produce enough torque to self-start the turbine and usually results in higher energy requirements. Their design comprised an aerofoil with a rigid core (spine), covered with flexible material that is free to deform under aerodynamic loading. Testing of a prototype highlighted that morphing enhanced the capability to self-starting. Nevertheless, it was found that the direction of morphing was dictated by the sum of the forces acting on the blade: as the turbine started rotating with higher angular velocities, the centrifugal force overcame the normal one and the blade morphed in an undesired shape thus increasing drag. This study underlines how passive morphing is an even greater challenge in the case of VATWs, due to the non-negligible centrifugal forces that may induce an adverse shape change of the aerofoils.

It is obvious that VATWs could also benefit from morphing. However, less research is conducted to develop suitable and advantageous designs for this specific type of turbines, due to their reduced popularity when compared to HATWs. It can also be understood that active morphing is the prevalent technique for VATWs, as centrifugal forces make the use of passive systems challenging.

5.3 Tidal turbines

Tidal turbines have recently attracted the interest of many researchers because of their high area-based power density [35]. However, due to the great thrust produced by the sea and ocean currents, tidal turbine blades usually experience very high stresses. Hence, morphing could alleviate loads and increase the fatigue life considerably.

Hoerner et al. [35] have proposed a promising passive morphing mechanism to alleviate loads and at the same time enhance the performance of a tidal turbine. In their study, flexible aerofoils that adapt their shape to the flow conditions were employed. This was done to delay flow separation and at the same time to reduce the dynamic stall caused by turbulence present in the water. A prototype was built and tested together with a fixed blade model (displayed in Figure 17) in a water tunnel with $200000 \leq Re \leq 300000$ and $3 \text{ m/s} \leq v_\infty \leq 3.5 \text{ m/s}$. The largest improvements

were observed at low TSRs, with a 25% reduction in structural loads and a 20% increase in thrust. Although a more detailed analysis on the material employed in this design should be carried out, as well as an investigation on the adverse effect of centrifugal forces on fatigue life (as highlighted in section 5.2), these experimental outcomes prove how beneficial passive morphing can be.

Figure 17: Conventional tidal turbine configuration [35].

Zeiner-Gundersen [44] conducted a study that led to very similar findings by running additional tests on a passive morphing blade for tidal turbines. In his analysis, the aerofoils consisted of a rigid carbon steel frame and a flexible pre-stretched polyvinyl skin, with a very high tear strength. By testing the prototype in a water tunnel at a variety of free stream velocities, a maximum C_p of 0.37, a really high value considering the efficiency of current tidal structures, was recorded. Moreover, the flexible hydrofoils allowed the turbine to self-start at very low stream speeds, hence increasing the energy production window. Although load alleviation was not quantified, this study confirmed the advantages that passive morphing has when implemented in tidal turbine applications.

To conclude, while active morphing techniques have been predominant for both HATWs and VATWs, passive ones seem to be prevailing in the case of tidal turbines. This is logical, because introducing complicated actuation systems that employ electro-mechanical mechanisms under water is a demanding challenge and would add mass to already very heavy structures. As a matter of fact, tidal turbines are usually much heavier than their earth-based counterparts as they are required to sustain the thrust produced by water, which is much denser than air. On the other hand, passive morphing is straightforward to implement, by letting the blades adjust themselves according to the water flow, and has proven to be beneficial both in terms of load alleviation and efficiency enhancement. Of course, as tidal turbines are still being developed and their industrial use is so far limited, only a few morphing concepts have been developed for such application.

6 Discussion

This paper has reviewed the most promising concepts developed for aircraft and turbine applications. Numerical simulations and small-scale experiments have confirmed the great benefits that morphing

has in terms of load alleviation and energy production enhancement. Nevertheless, there are some evident obstacles that still hinder the implementation of morphing designs in real applications.

As highlighted after assessing the results of most studies conducted in these fields, only a few authors manage to quantify the actuation time needed for the structure to deform in the desired shape. Actuation time is a crucial parameter and should be discussed more when attempting to design a morphing aerofoil. Indeed, the structure must be able to achieve the required shape change promptly, otherwise no load alleviation can occur. Of course, due to the available technology, a higher actuation speed usually corresponds to larger mechanisms which increase the weight of an aerofoil significantly, thus undermining the advantages associated with morphing.

Another issue is linked to the actuation systems themselves. Among the active morphing concepts presented in this paper, most of them employ servomotors or pulleys. These systems represent the most straightforward solution, especially when it comes to building prototypes for testing. Nevertheless, as argued in section 5.1, such apparatuses may not be appropriate for large-scale applications. Indeed, for a rotor blade, with a span length of 60 m-100 m, multiple servomotors/pulleys would be needed: such addition could correspond in a 20% increase in overall weight. Therefore, the research should focus on understanding how to implement alternative actuation systems comprising electro-active polymers or piezoelectric materials, that rapidly deform by generating internal strain fields when subjected to a current (*inverse piezoelectric effect*) [45]. Since electric charges can be carried quickly, with few losses and without the need of heavy cables or compliant structures, piezoelectric actuators would be significantly lighter and more efficient than conventional ones. Moreover, such mechanisms could be installed directly into the skin, so that the latter becomes the component responsible for actuation. This concept has already been examined by different researchers, such as Feng et al. [46]. Of course, these issues are avoided when employing bistable laminates for passive morphing aerofoils, however it was highlighted that numerous difficulties are associated with the manufacturing of such elements in large scale.

The other obstacle concerning morphing designs are skins. Most researchers deem preferable to use elastomers because of their great ductility and capability to undergo large deformations before yielding. Nevertheless, given their low strength, such materials are usually pre-stressed in order to avoid buckling. While this solution may be feasible for low cycle testing, it is surely not appropriate for long term applications such as the turbine ones due to creep phenomena. Hence, further investigation is required to assess what other materials could be employed for skins to be lightweight, stiff in the spanwise direction and flexible in the morphing one.

In order to completely overcome all the issues just highlighted, technology advancements are needed. Nonetheless, a valid and feasible morphing aerofoil that could actually be implemented in large-scale applications can be conceived by combining features from different proposed concepts. Of all the

reviewed designs, Ai et al. [38] have presented the most promising morphing aerofoil, clearly capable of outperforming the conventional discrete flaps, especially in terms of load alleviation. Their prototype featured the accordion honeycomb core mentioned in section 3.2, which conferred the ideal anisotropic properties discussed in section 2.2 to the whole structure. The CFRP rod, coupled with the servomotor, consisted of a simple way to induce deformation in the trailing edge. The energy requirements were limited (in proportion to the scale of the experimental model) and the actuation time was low. Nevertheless, the use of servomotors, as well as the silicon and CFRP skins, represented the flaws of this concept. That is why, this design should be combined with an electro-bonded laminate skin, described in section 3.1. The advantages of EBL are well known: they can reduce the input energy considerably, hence removing the need to have large actuation system. EBL could therefore result in smaller servomotors, decreasing the weight penalty and making the morphing concept suitable for large HATWs.

7 Conclusion

Humans have always dreamt of flying like birds. However, although advancements in technology have permitted flight, artificial structures still struggle to be as efficient and as versatile as the models of the animal kingdom. More specifically, engineering designs strive to emulate the physiognomy of the wings of insects, birds and especially bats, that possess the unique capacity to morph. Morphing allows these three animal species to constantly vary and adapt the shape of their wings to different flight conditions. This paper has shown how such ability, if translated into engineering terms, can result in structures characterised by a reduced mass, an increased aerodynamic efficiency and, more importantly, an enhanced fatigue life due to the lower stresses experienced.

The potential advantages of morphing have attracted many researchers in the aircraft industry and in the turbine energy production field. This paper has defined the fundamental properties that a morphing structure should have for such applications: be lightweight, have a high stiffness in the load bearing direction and be flexible in the morphing one. Therefore, a high level of anisotropy is needed to meet these criteria. Both the optimal skins and the ideal cores of a morphing aerofoil have been investigated. It has been found that electro-bonded laminates and overlapping polymer plates represent the best skin solutions. Regarding the cores, Zero Poisson's ratio accordion honeycomb cores have shown to be ideal for the considered scenarios.

The most promising morphing concepts that have been developed for the fields of interest of this research paper have been described, with a focus on horizontal axis wind turbines, vertical axis ones and, finally, tidal turbines. It has been found that in the case of wind turbines, both horizontal and vertical axis ones, active morphing designs that employ an actuation system prevail. Furthermore, it has been shown that many simulations and experiments have been conducted to assess the perfor-

mance of the proposed morphing aerofoils compared to those employing traditional control systems, such as discrete ailerons and pitching. In every case, morphing resulted in enhanced efficiency, with lower stresses experienced by structures and lower actuation energy requirements. Passive morphing concepts have also been inspected. Among them, the use of bistable elements has been reviewed. Such materials may represent a very beneficial solution, due to the absence of actuation systems and the ability to autonomously switch to different stable states. However, the manufacturing of large-scale bistable elements still represents a challenge for engineers, therefore testing of bigger size aerofoil prototypes is still unfeasible. Morphing concepts for tidal turbines focus mainly on passive techniques, with blades that are free to deform under the pressure of the water flow. This is rational, as installing actuation systems that employ electro-mechanical devices under water does not represent a straightforward task.

Of course, different morphing concept may result more appropriate for a specific type of turbine depending on the latter's characteristics. Nonetheless, this research paper has highlighted how the technique of cambering is predominant within the literature, as it is the morphing method that confers the greatest benefits to structures and requires smaller compliant systems to be achieved. As a matter of fact, other techniques such as twisting, which has been investigated thoroughly especially for helicopter applications, can result in the same advantages as cambering, yet only with non-negligible weight penalties that overshadow the benefits of morphing.

To conclude, morphing has shown to be a promising solution to alleviate loads and enhance the performance of helicopters, aeroplanes and turbines. However, morphing designs still display some relevant issues that hinder their deployment in large-scale applications. Indeed, researchers still focus on skins made of pre-tensioned elastomers as they are cheap and widely available: such solution may be suitable for short testing session with small-scale models, yet creep phenomena make it not appropriate for large structures that must have a high fatigue life. Nonetheless, the main issue regarding current (active) morphing concepts is the use of servomotors or pulleys as actuation systems. As a matter of fact, such components increase the overall weight of aerofoils substantially. While this may be a marginal concern during experiments, it becomes a fundamental matter when it comes to large-scale applications. Indeed, multiple servomotors or pulleys would be needed to induce morphing of the constantly growing blades of turbines: this would add considerable mass and thus outweigh the benefits of morphing. Therefore, the research should focus on new, more efficient and lighter actuation systems, that employ novel technologies such as piezoelectric materials and electro-active polymers. Further analysis should also be conducted on the manufacturing methods of bistable laminates.

In spite of the challenges, research and innovation are fast enough to let us expect that the compliant technology just discussed will reach a suitable level of readiness in the next lustrum, thus allowing morphing designs to be implemented in real applications before the end of this decade.

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